

Este documento complementa os dados apresentados no artigo intitulado “O que revelam os estudos secundários sobre chatbots na educação?”, apresentado e publicado nos anais do Simpósio Brasileiro de Informática na Educação (SBIE 2022).

Crítérios de seleção usados pelos estudos secundários

ID do estudo	Crítérios de seleção
e01	IC-1: The primary study presents at least one conversational agent to be used in the educational context.
	EC-1: The study is a technical report, a document, which is available in summary format, is a presentation, a call for papers or a summary of a conference.
	EC-2: The primary study is written in a language other than English.
	EC-3: The full text of the primary study is not available in the database.
	EC-4: The primary study does not meet the inclusion criteria.
e02	IC-1: Studies that had been peer-reviewed
	IC-2: Studies that describe some contributions of ITSs whose tutoring is based on dialogue with natural language
	IC-3: Studies that explain the main purpose of the dialogue; specify the adopted NLU approach
	IC-4: Studies that describe how the tutoring dialogue was conducted
	IC-5: Papers that described further details of their NLU approach or empirical studies related to them
	EC-1: studies that are surveys, not peer-reviewed, duplicated, or not written in English
	EC-2: if they describe conversational agents that have not been integrated into ITSs
	EC-3: if either their tutoring process or their NLU approach is not explained in sufficient detail
e03	IC-1: The presented system or application involved interactions in natural language with some form of computer or automated agent (this voluntarily broad definition will be refined in the next section).
	IC-2: Second language learning was the design goal of the system or of the study. A certain number of publications identified by the search were thus excluded from our study because language learning was only

	<p>mentioned as one of the potential fields of application (e.g. Griol, Molina, & Sanchis de Miguel, 2014). We also left apart a few studies applied to primary language acquisition, either for children (e.g. Kim, 2013) or to adult communicative skills development (Vaassen et al., 2012).</p>
	<p>IC-3: The above-mentioned system or its application to language learning was the main focus of the publication. This excluded certain papers that only mentioned the existence or the possibility of a dialogue system (e.g. Lorenzo, Lezcano, & Sanchez-Alonso, 2013), presented a technological component, such as a parser or a dialogue manager, but whose application to dialogue-based CALL was not discussed (e.g. Chen & Tokuda, 2003), as well as reviews of CALL that only briefly mentioned dialogue applications.</p>
	<p>IC-4: The document was a peer-reviewed publication – papers published in a peer-reviewed journal or presented at an international conference, or chapter in an edited book – or a doctoral dissertation.</p>
	<p>EC-1: Papers that could not be accessed online or in major university libraries, papers written in languages we could not understand (Korean, Chinese), and a couple of duplicate versions of papers that were already included (republications).</p>
e04	<p>IC-1: Research articles that focus on pedagogical conversation agents. We only included results targeting educational settings, which is reflected in the search terms.</p>
	<p>EC-1: Remove irrelevant articles based on review of titles and abstracts</p>
	<p>EC-2: Remove research articles that not evaluated pedagogical conversational agents or that not give insights into their evaluation approach</p>
e05	<p>IC-1: The study must refer to educational chatbots or chatbots used in education to improve existing services</p>
	<p>IC-2: Some of the following key points about the chatbots must be discussed: the design or technology employed, their success or failure in implementation, successful improvements or problems encountered, whether they require prior training, the roles assigned to the chatbots</p>
	<p>IC-3: The study must present ways to evaluate chatbots in a generic way (e.g., as technology tools) or chatbots that are educationally oriented, that is, can be evaluated as educational tools</p>
	<p>IC-4: There must be comparison between natural language processor (NLP) employed in the chatbots.</p>
	<p>EC-1: Studies on chatbots used in noneducational or nonresearch related settings were excluded</p>

	EC-2: Studies on chatbots whose description, use or design was unclear were excluded
	EC-3: Conference papers published in a language other than English were excluded
	EC-4: Studies whose full text was not available
	EC-5: Studies that did not have well-defined Methods, Results, or Conclusions sections

Palavras-chave que constituem as strings de busca dos estudos secundários

ID do estudo	Palavras-chave
e01	(“conversational agent” OR chatbot OR “chat bot” OR chatterbot OR “dialogue system” OR “pedagogical agent” OR “virtual agent” OR “virtual assistant”) AND (education OR learn OR pedagogic OR teach)
e02	(“Intelligent Tutoring*” OR “Tutor*” OR “Pedagogical Agent” OR “Intelligent Learning Environment”) AND (“Dialogue* ” OR “Tutorial Dialogue System” OR “Natural Language * ” OR “Conversational”) AND (“Teaching” OR “Educational Training” OR “Procedural Training”)
e03	(chatbot/chat bot/chatterbot/conversational agent/ conversational companion/conversational system/dialog system/dialog agent/dialog game/pedagogical agent/humancomputer dialog/dialog-based) AND ((language/English) (learning/teaching/acquisition)/(second/foreign) language/L2/EFL/ESL/ICALL)
e04	(“pedagogical conversational agent”) AND (“smart teaching assistant” OR “AI teaching assistant” OR “artificial intelligence teachin assistant” OR “virtual teaching assistant” AND (chatbot OR chatterbot OR talkbot OR “interactive agent” OR “dialog system” OR “conversatioal agent”) AND (learning OR teaching)

e05	“chatbot” OR “conversational agent” OR “conversational tutor” OR “bot” AND (“learning” OR “education”)
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Bases de dados consideradas pelos estudos secundários

ID do estudo	Base de dados
e01	ACM Digital Library
	Elsevier (Science Direct)
	Engineering Village
	IEEE Xplore
	Scopus
	Web of Science
e02	ACM Digital Library
	Elsevier (Science Direct)
	IEEE Xplore
	Scopus
	Semantic Scholar
	SpringerLink
e03	Web of Science
	ProQuest
	Scopus
e04	ACM Digital Library
	AIS Electronic Library
	AISSenior Scholars’ Basket of Journals
	EBSCOhost Business Source Complete
	IEEE Xplore Digital Library

	Science Direct
	DeLFI Proceedings
e05	IEEE Xplore
	Elsevier (Science Direct)
	Scopus
	ACM Digital Library
	Web of Science
	Education Resources Information Center
	Wiley Online Library
	Google Scholar
	Google
	ResearchGate.net